

GUD: a new Modern Greek treebank enriched with VMWE annotations

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1 Introduction

We report on *UD_Greek-GUD* (henceforth GUD), the most recent *Universal Dependencies* (UD) treebank of *Standard Modern Greek* (SMG). GUD adheres to UD.v2 (de Marneffe et al., 2021) and is the first SMG UD treebank to annotate *Verbal Multiword Expressions* (VMWE). We describe the language material and the special annotation features of GUD. We also report on ongoing work on training models on GUD and establishing an evaluation method for their predictions about VMWE.

2 Materials and annotation method

UD_Greek-GDT (henceforth GDT) (Prokopidis and Papageorgiou, 2017) is the first UD treebank of SMG. Both GUD and GDT have been manually annotated for morphology and syntax, and GUD is annotated for VMWE as well.

To develop GUD, 1,807 sentences (25,493 tokens) have been randomly selected from fiction texts. Also, 723 sentences (13,111 tokens) were retrieved from IDION (Markantonatou et al., 2019), an open-source web database of SMG VMWE. These usage examples of the VMWE have been collected over the last 15 years with Google searches from social media, football sites, etc., where colloquial SMG is used. The ArboratorGrew tool¹ was used to implement the annotation.

Annotation of GUD was done by graduate students in Language Technology (2021-2024) and was supervised by two of the authors.

3 What is new about GUD

GUD and GDT share the same tokenization and word segmentation guidelines but differ notably in terms of morphological and syntactic annotation.

Morphological annotation: The main differences regarding the morphological annotation of the two treebanks are:

1. *na*, *pou* (≥ 300 and ≤ 200 occurrences in GUD

respectively) introduce sentential complements of verbs. *pou* is also used to introduce relative clauses and some types of adverbial clauses. *na* is also used to form periphrastic imperatives, express wishes, curses, etc., as well as other constructions, e.g., for pointing to something. GDT tagged *pou* as PRON and *na* as AUX. GUD tags *pou* as SCONJ when it introduces sentential complements of verbs (Joseph and Philippaki-Warburton, 1987), (Joseph, 1981) and with PRON when it introduces relative clauses. For *na*, GUD uses the tag SCONJ when *na* introduces sentential complements of verbs, the tag AUX when it introduces main clauses expressing orders, wishes, curses, etc., and the tag PART in clauses with deixis.

2. GUD adheres closely to the UD.v2 morphological guidelines and assigns the tag DET to 39 lemmas while GDT assigns it to 17.

3. GUD, but not GDT, annotates diminutives and augmentatives on nouns, adjectives, and adverbs. GUD assigns the lemma without a diminutive (or augmentative) affix to forms both with and without a diminutive (or augmentative) affix.

4. GUD tags passive participles as VERB, and GDT as ADJ. In GUD, participles not related to a verb in use are tagged as ADJ.

5. GUD does not use the case tag DAT because the dative is found only in fixed expressions.

6. GUD tags fossilised types from the diachrony of Greek with the UPOS X.

7. GDT and GUD use different sets of auxiliaries.

8. Contrary to GDT, GUD provides exhaustive annotation of both periphrastic and morphological degrees of comparison in SMG.

Syntactic annotation: Specific to GUD are the relations `advcl:relcl`, `dislocated`, and `nsubj:outer`. Contrary to GDT, GUD does not use the relation `dep`.

GUD, but not GDT, analyses the contracted forms *ston*, *stin*, *sto*, *stous*, *stis*, *sta*. These forms occur with ditransitive verbs and are contractions of two pronouns: one in the genitive case, functioning as the indirect object of the verb, and a second pronoun in the accusative case functioning as the

¹<https://arborator.github.io/>

direct object of the same verb. These contractions, although identical in form, are different from the adposition *se* plus the definite article contractions.

4 Verbal MWE annotation

GUD contains 723 sentences (28% of the total GUD sentences) featuring 100 VMWE, mainly of the verbal idiom type, some light verb constructions, and some verb-particle ones (see the PARSEME typology by Savary et al. 2018). The sentences exemplify flexible usages of the VMWE in terms of morphology, word order permutations of the lexicalised parts of the VMWE, insertion, and lexical variant pairs.

VMWE annotation is in the spirit of Savary et al. (2023) and draws on a suggestion by D. Zeman. It is inserted in the MISC (10th) column of the CoNLLU representation of the sentence. PARSEME has used an 11th column (CoNLLU Plus format specifications).² Annotation tools, e.g., Arborator-Grew, and analysis tools, e.g., Stanza (Qi et al., 2020), allow for 10 columns only. We used a script that reads MWE annotations off the 10th column and attaches the type of the MWE as a subrelation on the corresponding syntactic relations in the 8th column. The model is expected to predict VMWE subrelation labels attached to the syntactic relation labels in the 8th column. Example 1 offers a picture of the treebank VMWE annotation before the application of the script, while Examples 2 and 3 illustrate the format after the script has been applied.

5 Experiments

We trained Stanza models in four settings: three settings with GUD plus 723, 500 and 300 sentences featuring ≥ 1 VMWE and one with 723 sentences featuring ≥ 1 VMWE. (Embeddings: GUD+GreekBert). We have used only one test set with 200 sentences featuring ≥ 1 VMWE and 242 VMWE occurrences in all. Most of the test sentences featured a VMWE that does not occur in the train set but is a lexical variant of a VMWE in the train set. The test sentences were selected to contain different forms of the same VMWE in terms of morphology of the head verb, distance among, and word order of the lexicalised parts. The results shown in Table 1 indicate a coherent annotation

of the GUD and the VMWE usage examples although the GUD+723 setting indicates that certain inconsistencies still exist.

Setting ¹	Lemma	UPOS	UFEATS	UAS	LAS
GUD+723	90.99	94.78	87.18	88.03	81.62
GUD+500	90.99	94.97	87.80	87.94	82.27
GUD+300	90.23	94.69	86.93	88.03	81.25
723	90.12	94.01	86.39	86.67	78.94

Table 1: Performance metrics for four settings.

¹723/500/300 sentences featuring at least one VMWE.

In CoNLLU, a sentence is represented with the contents of a table with 10 columns and a set of rows numbered from 1 to m , $m > 1$. The representation of a VMWE with l , $l \leq m$ lexicalised components in column 8, could be a set of not necessarily contiguous table cells containing information about VMWE (a sentence may contain ≥ 1 VMWE): $VMWE_x^{C8} = \{r_{i_1}^{C8}, r_{i_2}^{C8}, \dots, r_l^{C8}\}$ and in column 10: $VMWE_x^{C10} = \{r_{i_1}^{C10}, r_{i_2}^{C10}, \dots, r_l^{C10}\}$, where in both cases $i_1 < i_2 < \dots < l \wedge i_n, l, m, n, x \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots\} \wedge i_{n+1} - i_n \geq 1$. These simplified definitions do not consider the exact contents of the cells.

We measure recall ($R=TP/(TP+FN)$) and precision ($P=TP/(TP+FP)$) of the model trained on GUD+723 in two ways:

1. **Per-token.** Taking advantage of the tabular format of CoNLLU, we use the following definitions (see also Savary et al. 2018,38):

TP if $r_i^{C8} \in VMWE_x^{C8} \wedge r_i^{C10} \in VMWE_x^{C10}$
 FP if $r_i^{C8} \in VMWE_x^{C8} \wedge r_i^{C10} \notin VMWE_x^{C10}$
 FN if $r_i^{C8} \notin VMWE_x^{C8} \wedge r_i^{C10} \in VMWE_x^{C10}$
 (for all cases above $1 \leq i \leq l \leq m$).

Per-token recall: 0.84. Per-token precision: 0.94

2. **Per-VMWE.** A Per-VMWE TP occurs if for all $r_i^{C10} \in VMWE_x^{C10}$ there is a Per-token TP. However, Per-token FPs may be adjacent to Per-VMWE TPs blurring the boundaries of the VMWE, and this is an evaluation aspect that we plan to investigate in the immediate future. A Per-VMWE FN occurs when there is at least one $r_i^{C10} \in VMWE_x^{C10}$ that has a Per-token FN. Per-VMWE FP cannot be defined because we can identify only the VMWE that are represented in column 10. Per-VMWE recall: 0.53.

VMWE recall was reasonable, given the many variant forms and the lexical variants of the train VMWE in the test set. We plan to experiment with larger test sets and corpora with more MWE

²<https://universaldependencies.org/ext-format.html>

types. We also plan to experiment by dissociating the VMWE subrelations from syntax, probably by encoding them in the (empty) XPOS column.

The GUD treebank serves as a valuable linguistic resource for knowledge transfer across several Greek dialects, supporting the morphological and syntactic analysis of cases with limited resources. In addition, incorporating MWEs in the treebank could significantly enhance other downstream tasks, such as offensive language detection, which relies heavily on contextual understanding. We anticipate that MWE-informed models will be more effective at recognizing phrases within their context, leading to more accurate and reliable results across a variety of language processing tasks.

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6 Appendices

pou mas echis afisi sixilous stous pente dromous
because us have.2.SING left petrified in.the five roads
'because you have astounded and abandoned us'

```
# text = που μας έχεις αφήσει σύξυλους στους πέντε δρόμους.  
18 που που SCONJ PnRe _ 21 mark _ _  
19 μας εγώ PRON PnPe Case=AccI|Number=Plur|Person=1|PronType=Prs 21 obj _ _  
20 έχεις έχω AUX VbMn Mood=IndI|Number=Sing|Person=2|Tense=Pres|VerbForm=Fin|Voice=Act 21 aux _ _  
21 αφήσει αφήνω VERB VbMn Aspect=PerfI|Mood=IndI|VerbForm=InfI|Voice=Act 2 advcl _ mwe=1,2:VID  
22 σύξυλους σύξυλος ADJ AjBa Case=AccI|Gender=Masc|Number=Plur 21 xcomp _ mwe=1  
23 στους στου ADP AsPpSp Case=AccI|Gender=Masc|Number=Plur 25 case _ mwe=2  
24 πέντε πέντε NUM NmCd Case=AccI|Gender=Masc|Number=Plur|NumType=Card 25 nummod _ mwe=2  
25 δρόμους δρόμος NOUN NoCm Case=AccI|Gender=Masc|Number=Plur 21 obl _ mwe=2:VID  
26 . . PUNCT PTERMP _ 2 punct _ PunctType=Peri
```

Example 1: Annotation of 2 conflated VMWE with the same verb head and different lexicalised parts (sixilous, pente dromous).

den vgike pote apo to mialo mou kai oute prokeitai
it never left.3.SING my mind and it will not
'It never left my mind and it will not'

```
# text = Δεν βγήκε ποτέ από το μυαλό μου και ούτε πρόκειται.  
1 Δεν δεν PART PtNg Polarity=Neg 2 advmod _ _  
2 βγήκε βγαίνω VERB VbMn Aspect=PerfI|Mood=IndI|Number=Sing|Person=3|Tense=Past|VerbForm=Fin|Voice=Act 0 root:vid _ mwe=1:VID  
3 ποτέ ποτέ ADV AdBa _ 2 advmod _ None=Yes  
4 από από ADP AsPpSp _ 6 case:vid _ mwe=1|None=Yes  
5 το ο DET AtDf Case=AccI|Definite=DefI|Gender=Neut|Number=Sing|PronType=Art 6 det:vid _ mwe=1  
6 μυαλό μυαλό NOUN NoCm Case=AccI|Gender=Neut|Number=Sing 2 obl:vid _ mwe=1  
7 μου εγώ PRON PnPo Case=GenI|Number=Sing|Person=1|Poss=Yes|PronType=Prs 6 nmod _ _  
8 και και CCONJ CjCo _ 10 cc _ None=Yes  
9 ούτε ούτε PART PtNg Polarity=Neg 10 advmod _ None=Yes  
10 πρόκειται πρόκειται VERB VbMn Aspect=Impl|Mood=IndI|Number=Sing|Person=3|Tense=Pres|VerbForm=Fin|Voice=Pass 2 conj _ _  
11 . . PUNCT PTERMP _ 2 punct _ PunctType=Peri
```

Example 2: Output produced by the Stanza model.

o pichis gia fetos echi anevi poli psila
the bar for this.year has risen very high
'The bar for this year has risen very high'

```
# text = Ο πήχυς για φέτος έχει ανέβει πολύ ψηλά  
1 Ο ο DET AtDf Case=NomI|Definite=DefI|Gender=Masc|Number=Sing|PronType=Art 2 det:vid _ mwe=1  
2 πήχυς πήχης NOUN NoCm Case=NomI|Gender=Masc|Number=Sing 6 obj:vid _ mwe=1  
3 για για ADP AsPpSp _ 6 case _ None=Yes  
4 φέτος φέτος ADV AdBa _ 3 fixed _ _  
5 έχει έχω AUX VbMn Mood=IndI|Number=Sing|Person=3|Tense=Pres|VerbForm=Fin 6 aux _ _  
6 ανέβει ανέβω VERB VbMn Aspect=PerfI|Mood=IndI|Number=Sing|Person=3|VerbForm=Fin|Voice=Act 0 root:vid _ mwe=1:VID  
7 πολύ πολύ ADV AdBa _ 8 advmod _ None=Yes  
8 ψηλά ψηλά ADV AdBa _ 6 advmod _ _
```

Example 3: Output produced by the Stanza model.